

DURABILITY OF GLASS-VINYLESTER COMPOSITES EXPOSED TO SEAWATER AND CORROSIVE FLUID

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ABSTRACT

Epoxy based composite materials are known to exhibit good resistance to seawater and corrosive fluids. This was the result of an extensive research work. However such systems are not cost effective for applications where large amounts of materials are needed, such as the oil industry and the infrastructure market. For that reason alternative material systems such as Glass/vinylester composites are potential candidates. However, extensive research is needed to evaluate the durability of these composites when exposed to seawater and corrosive fluids.

In this paper, Glass/vinylester specimens were immersed in seawater and a corrosive fluid with different concentration for a six months period. Then the specimens were subjected to tensile testing to evaluate their mechanical properties while fractured surfaces were analyzed using the scanning electron microscope (SEM).

KEYWORDS: Glass vinylester composites, corrosive fluid, seawater durability and scanning electron microscope (SEM).

INTRODUCTION

The durability of Glass reinforced composite materials is an important issue, especially for structures used in a marine environment or exposed to corrosive fluids. For example, chemical corrosion of glass fibers is dependent on many factors such as stress level, acid concentration and temperature of the environment. Accordingly, much research focused on understanding and quantifying these phenomena. A class of composite materials, i.e., glass reinforced vinylester composites, are considered an efficient and cost effective material system for applications requiring large amount of materials. However, little is known about the performance of this material system when exposed to seawater and corrosive fluids. Accordingly, there is a need to investigate the behavior of such a material system. Therefore, it is anticipated through this research, to clarify and identify the mechanisms responsible for the degradation of the mechanical properties of the material and to what extent longer immersion periods and different fluid concentration can affect its performance.

Following this introduction, a review of current research is presented, followed by material and experimental set-up. Finally results are analyzed and discussed with emphasis on the changes taking place on the micro-structural level through the use of electron microscopy.

The propagation characteristics of stress corrosion surface cracks and crack growth rates in a range of unidirectional glass/polyester composites exposed to 0.6 N dilute HCl acid were examined using a fracture mechanics test [1]. Although, the composites when subjected to no mechanical stress, were offering a good resistance to corrosion, appreciable deterioration was observed for specimens degraded mechanically and exposed to a corrosive environment. In the stress corrosion tests, if the selected load is high enough to lead to debonding; the coefficient of diffusion will be increased. As a result of debonding, the attack of the environment spread to the uncracked region of fibers leads to degradation.

Chemical corrosion of glass fibers (E and C) was monitored under creep testing using acoustic emission [2]. Different failure mechanisms were observed for C and E glass. E glass specimen

exhibited a flat surface, which is evidence of acid stress corrosion. For C glass specimens, fracture was initiated by fiber pullout thus indicating occurrence of damage to the fiber resin interface. In similar work that was done [3] to understand the crack-propagation behavior under the acid stress environment, it was concluded that this behavior is dependent on many factors such as stress level, acid concentration and temperature of the environment. Results have shown that crack propagation behavior in water was largely enhanced in comparison with that in the air and it was almost as pronounced as that in the acid solution. It is suggested that the E/VE system degradation in the fiber was because of acid diffusion and the C/VE systems at the load-sharing rate of the fibers was because of the water absorption, which greatly contributes to crack propagation. Crack propagation in fiber reinforced composites under stress corrosion cracking conditions was also investigated [4] under constant and cyclic loading tests. It was found that cyclic loading and acid concentration will affect the crack propagation rate. When analyzing the fractured surfaces, fiber matrix interfacial debonding was identified as the main failure mechanism. Corrosion behavior and mechanisms of glass fiber reinforced polyester composites in acidic solution (30 % wt nitric acid) were investigated [5]. Corrosion behavior evolved according to the following: first surface reaction then formation of a corroded layer followed by penetration. The corrosion mechanisms are physical degradation by swelling, the formation of pits, oxidation corrosion and finally hydrolytic corrosion. Following the formation of a corroded layer, blisters are generated and start growing by swelling pressure until final collapse. Initiator and plasticizer contents were identified as playing a major role in the resin performance in acidic solution. The seawater durability of carbon and glass reinforced polyester and vinylester composites were investigated [6]. The composites were virtually identical in terms of fabrication processing, dimensions, thickness and fiber volume fraction, and this allowed the effect of fiber type and resin type on durability to be determined. Results revealed that 4 days^{1/2} of immersion is the maximum weight gain time. Beyond this point, a gradual decline in the mass change curves occurs. This is thought to be an irreversible chemical degradation process of composite. Room temperature cured composites were found to have less weight gain than the fully cured specimen. This may be due to leaching out of the unreacted species into the seawater. Fully cured carbon reinforced polyester composite was seen to absorb less water than fully cured glass reinforced polyester. Additional water uptake of the fiber resin interface is behind this difference. However, for glass/vinyl ester and carbon/vinyl ester composites at room temperature, the water uptake curves sharply increases when immersed in seawater instantaneously because of the rapid absorption of water. After that uptake, it was observed that the composite continued steadily absorbing extra water although at a slower rate. The difference between this behavior and the polyester based composites behavior is thought to be due to the greater resistance of the vinyl ester to the hydrolytic degradation when compared to the polyester [6]. It is clear that the durability of fiber reinforced composites remains an open subject that deserve further investigation especially for the new opportunities offered to composites in the oil industry and infrastructure structures. Although, tangible results were achieved, further research is needed to fully understand the mechanisms that affect the performance of these materials.

MATERIALS AND SAMPLE PREPARATION

Samples were made using the hot press molding technique. The reinforcement used was a woven roving E-glass, which is a coarse drapable fabric in which continuous roving are woven into two mutually perpendicular directions. The reinforcement has a surface weight density of 500 g/m² and an average filament diameter of 12 μm. Each stack consists of ten plies. The samples produced were squares having an edge of 150 mm. A steel frame was used to provide the desired thickness for the stack. The resin used is a vinyl ester resin: EPOVIA RF 1001HV, which is a high-viscosity type resin, supplied by Cray Valley. The vinyl ester was promoted with 3 pph of a cobalt octoate solution and catalyzed with 1.5 pph of 50% methyl ethyl ketone peroxide. The degree of cure of the composite samples was checked using a Barcol hardness test and a value between 50 and 60 was recorded.

The samples were then divided into groups each one containing thirty samples. Each of the groups was exposed to a specific environment. While some samples were immersed in seawater, others were subject to a corrosive fluid (nitric acid) with different concentrations. All samples were exposed for three and six month periods.

TESTING AND RESULTS ANALYSIS

Different properties such as flexural strength and modulus as well as interlaminar shear strength and impact properties were evaluated using three point bending test as recommended by ASTM Standard (ASTM D3039- 00). Typical results for different mechanical properties obtained are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: *Typical results for corrosive fluids performance*

Flexural Strength (Mpa)	575	593	461	513	496	463	433
Flexural Modulus (Mpa)	19715	22192	18072	19029	21553	19386	20402
Properties	Corrosive fluids						
	Virgin	Seawater		2%nitri acid		5%Nitric acid	
		3 months	6 months	3 months	6 months	3 months	6 months
Glass Content (%)	76.4	76.4	77.0	76.4	75.0	76.4	74.6
Impact Strength (KJ/m ²)	68.3	63.0	63.3	66.9	No	63.5	No
ILSS(Mpa)	31.6	29.3	32.99	32.7	32.54	31.8	29.32

When comparing the results for virgin specimen with those obtained after three months and six months period, the following observations were noted:

- For specimens exposed to nitric acid, there was a significant effect of acid concentration and immersion time on the mechanical properties. Increasing immersion times will result in a significant decrease in the flexural strength, i.e., 13.2 % (2%) and 24.6% (5%). Although these figures can be reduced through a reduction in the fiber volume fraction in order to offer better protection to the fiber matrix interface, it is clear that by increasing the concentration of medium, acceleration occurs in the degradation process. Other researchers who noticed degradation in the physical properties of composite following a longer immersion time also confirmed the trend observed here. Also concentration of the medium was also affecting the composite long-term performance.
- The interlaminar shear strength values recorded for various composites specimens were almost identical, although some decrease occurred for specimens exposed to higher acid concentration. Occurrence of internal micro-cracks may explain such drop in the interlaminar shear strength values.
- For specimens exposed to seawater, it was clear that long immersion time would result in a decrease in the flexural modulus. This was confirmed by the recorded 18.5 % drop in the flexural modulus values between the three and six months period. For the durability in seawater, water diffusion through the matrix is the main degradation mechanism. Although, the diffusion is expected to reach a saturation level (equilibrium), it is possible for many resins systems that this level will never be reached and water absorption may continue for months or even years [6]. Weight gain of the composite specimen as a function of moisture exposure duration is shown in Figure 1. It can be seen that weight gain of the composite increased significantly during the early stage of immersion then continued in a steady state regime. For the total immersed period, the gain weight reached 2.5%.

Figure 1: composite weight gain

Surface of fractured virgin specimens and specimens exposed to different environments were examined using Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM). This is done in order to evaluate the failure mechanisms involved. From the analysis of the fractured surfaces, it is clear that different mechanisms such as debonding, delamination and cracks growth were involved in the composite fracture.

Starting with the virgin specimens shown in Figures 2-5, the following observations can be drawn:

- The specimens produced have a relatively high fiber content, which may affect the quality of the interface between the fibers and matrix. For that reason, poor bonding may result at the interface between the fiber and matrix. Accordingly, layer delamination and fiber pullout are identified as the predominant failure mechanisms. Also, at higher magnification, resin spots appeared on the fiber surface, which look like blisters. At this time, it is not possible to conclude whether these spots were produced following a chemical reaction between the fiber sizing and the resin or not.

Figure 2: SEM image showing high Fiber content and layer delamination

Figure 3: SEM image showing fiber pull-out

Figure 4: SEM image showing resins spots on the fiber surface

Figure 5: Resin spots distribution over the surface of the fiber.

- For specimens immersed in nitric acid, scanning electron microscope images have shown to what extent the severity of the medium may affect the composite specimens regardless of the acid concentration. It is clear that the degradation takes place via two stages; in the first stage resin is attacked under the combined action of water diffusion and the presence of H^+ . In the second stage the fiber itself is attacked and cracks appear on the fiber surface, as shown in Figure 6. Furthermore composite layers delamination occurs resulting in large opening between two successive layers, as shown in Figure 7 by the white arrows, which affects the composite resistance to loading stresses.

Figure 6: SEM image showing cracks on the fiber surface

Figure 7: SEM image showing composite layers delamination

- For specimens immersed in seawater, the main failure mechanism is caused by water absorption and diffusion. The resin starts absorbing water, which results in a volumetric expansion that leads to micro cracks. The latter propagate, as shown in Figure 8. Once propagation starts, fiber failure occurs. Previous work [6] has shown that degradation of vinyl ester based composites when immersed in seawater may occur by the leaching out of unreacted chemicals from the resin matrix into seawater and the extent of this decrease with the degree of cure of the resin. A direct consequence of this is a poor interface between the fiber and matrix as shown in Figure 9.

Figure 8: SEM image showing micro-matrix cracks on the composite surface

Figure 9: SEM showing poor fiber-matrix interface

CONCLUSION

This work was concerned with the evaluation of the durability of fiber-reinforced composites based on vinyl ester resin when exposed to seawater and corrosive fluids. Although the duration of exposure cannot be classified as a long term exposure, it was possible to obtain some results by accelerating the degradation process, thus mechanisms for material degradation and performance under severe conditions can be established.

Specimens were divided into different groups that were subject to different immersion and exposure time. Then testing was performed using three point bending test. Results of conditioned specimens were compared to virgin specimens to assess the extent of composite degradation.

After reviewing the results and SEM images of fractured specimens the following conclusions can be drawn:

- A relatively high fiber content may prevent the matrix from fully impregnating the fiber. Under these conditions, micro-cracks may appear at the interface between the fiber and the matrix. Such micro-cracks under the combined action of water diffusion and hydrogen ions may accelerate the degradation process.
- For specimens immersed in seawater, uncured chemical agents were easily leached out thus leaving the fibers with no protection. Such situations will contribute to the poor performance of the specimens. In addition interlaminar shear strength may

decrease significantly as a consequence of the poor bonding between the fiber and the matrix.

- For corrosive fluids, it is clear that by increasing the medium concentration and immersion time, the performance of the composite specimens will change drastically. The combined action of water and the corrosive fluid leads to matrix expansion and the occurrence of pits. The latter after longer immersion time may form blisters, which may start growing by swelling pressure until final collapse.

Although immersion time was not long enough to elucidate all the mechanisms affecting the durability of fiber reinforced composites based on vinyl ester resins, it was possible to recognize the main mechanisms involved. Also, processing and conditioning of the composite samples affect drastically the performance of the composite.

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